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Author(s): Salvatore Scifo (KU), Lemi Baruh (KU)
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The efficient use of new information and communication technologies can be of crucial importance in emergency response and crisis communications. New media applications are able to perform a range of functions such as facilitating two-way communication, enabling citizens and first responders to request/offer assistance, enhance campaigning activities for fund raising purposes, and enable individuals/groups to efficiently organize for action. Likewise, social networking, crowdsourcing, and data mining technologies offer new means through which different stakeholders, such as officials, responders, citizens, can gather and disseminate information so as to optimize emergency response.

Yet, new media technologies, and particularly social media, may often be misused, either intentionally or unintentionally in ways that can impede efficient communication during emergencies and crises. The present “Report on the adverse use and reliability of new media” (D2.3) aims to provide an overview the adverse use of new media by scammers, hackers, terrorist groups, ordinary citizens, as well as, at times, government authorities and companies. The report also aims to provide an in-depth discussion of an issue that users of new media technologies face in the utilization of such technologies during crises and emergencies: reliability of information. Following a brief introduction (Chapter 1), the report will comprise three chapters.

In Chapter 2, the report will focus on types of misuse of new media and their management. The first two sections of Chapter 2 will consider misuse of new media technologies along two axes: types of misuse and players in misuse. In the first section of the chapter, the report will focus on are *misrepresentation, rumor spreading, propaganda, surveillance and censorship, and lateral surveillance*. After discussing these misuse types, the section to follow will proceed with an analysis of key “players” in misuse of new media technologies. Using examples from case studies of emergencies and crises conducted by the COSMIC team in Deliverable 2.2., as well as examples form other recent emergencies and crises (such as the Arab Spring and Hurricane Katrina) the chapter will describe the role that *scammers, hackers, government authorities*, and private corporations may play both as misusers and responders, depending on the circumstances.

In the final section of Chapter 2, the report will discuss how different stakeholders try to manage misuse of new media. In terms of management of misuse, the report distinguished between external threats as those that come from the outside a given system or organization and internal threats that come from within an organization. In this section, particular attention has been paid to the concept of *sousveillance*, which can be defined as surveillance from below (performed by the public on institutions) as an approach that can increase the accountability of powerful players and prevent abuse of power. Also, the report discussed new countersurveillance techniques that can protect citizens’ right to privacy and free speech at times of crises (specifically political crises). Finally, discussion of management of internal threats underlined how datamining techniques can be used for early detection and prevention of misuse during times of crises.

An important lesson learned from the discussion on Chapter 2 is that in many cases, while trying to respond to potential misuses of information, various stakeholders, including government authorities, may themselves hinder effective utilization of new media technologies for crises communication. Hence, a proper approach to management of misuse

of new media technologies should definitely involve multitude of stakeholders, and particularly supranational organizations, that can provide a system of checks and balances.

The focus of Chapter 3 was dissemination of misinformation via new media technologies at times of crises and techniques that can be used by various stakeholders (including citizens and mainstream journalists) to verify information. In this chapter, specific attention was paid to primary data collected from Internet users about reliability of information during the Gezi Protests that took place in Turkey in 2013. The findings from these data suggest that while Internet users are aware of the potential pitfalls of relying on the Internet for information about crises and emergencies, they often see the Internet as a more viable choice for up to date information when compared to mainstream media. Moreover, the data suggests that a considerable proportion of users engage in techniques to actively verify the information they receive. However, some of these techniques may end up amplifying the problem of dissemination of misinformation. As such, development and widespread adoption of technologies that can assist stakeholders in information verification is needed. Given this need, Chapter 3 concludes with an overview of some of the technologies (e.g., Semantically Interlinked Online Communities-SIOC), applications (e.g., Hoodcast) and techniques (crowdsourcing) that can be viable options to assist not only citizens but all stakeholders who utilize new media for getting information during times of emergencies and crises.

Based on these analyses, the last chapter (Conclusion) provides a summary of key insights regarding misuse of new media technologies during crisis, management of misuse and information verification. Also, the last chapter proposes a set of principles that can guide future efforts to alleviate the adverse uses of new media described in the report.

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital media and information technologies have been increasingly utilized by members of response agencies, government authorities, as well as the public, to communicate information and coordinate action during crises. Commenting on this potential of new media technologies in crisis communications, Meier recently opined that “disasters are collective experiences; and today, disaster-affected crowds are increasingly ‘digital crowds’ as well—that is, both a source and consumer of that digital information. In other words, they are also the first *digital responders*.”¹

Especially in cases when much of conventional communication infrastructures are strained due to overload or are damaged, new media applications can certainly be of great assistance in increasing the efficiency of emergency response and crisis communications. Elsewhere in COSMIC, the opportunities brought about by new media technologies were discussed extensively.²

Despite new media technologies’ potential as tools that can assist emergency response, their improper use remains an important challenge in emergency communications during a crisis. For example, new media are open to use by scammers, hackers and other people who might intentionally harm or manipulate other people in a situation of crisis. Also, government authorities, members of the public, and response organizations may inadvertently misutilize these new technologies in ways that impede emergency response.

Accordingly, this report will focus on the adverse use of ICTs during crises and issues related to information verification in the context of new media, two areas that acquired significance especially along with the growth in the use of social media to publish, share and circulate information during a crisis. In this context, this report will also discuss how various tools can help stakeholders, including citizens, response agencies, and government authorities to find reliable information or verify information received from those using social media.

¹ “Using Waze, Uber, AirBnB and SeeClickFix for Disaster Response”, *iRevolution*, 11 June 2013. <http://irevolution.net/2013/06/11/uber-waze-airbnb-seeclickfix-for-disaster-response/>

² Kotsiopoulos, Alex et al., “Deliverable 3.2.1: Political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies”, *COSMIC*, 2013, pp.31-34.

2. ADVERSE USES OF MEDIA

2.1. INTRODUCTION

The first chapter of this report will discuss the adverse use of new media technologies, starting with an outline of the types of misuse, including misrepresentation, propaganda, rumour, and their use for purposes of surveillance and censorship.

It will then proceed to illustrate the role (negative as well as positive) of different players, including hackers, scammers, government authorities and private corporations, involved in the misuse of new media through a range of examples that show the practical implications and consequences of new media misuse in the context of crises.

The final part will then focus on the practice of managing and mismanaging the misuse of new media in the context of the management of external threats, by discussing how governments and the public are involved, actively and passively, in forms of lateral surveillance, sousveillance, and counterveillance. Briefly, the management of internal threats and the importance of the early detection of potential harmful insider behaviour, and its implications in crisis management will be also discussed.

2.2. TYPES OF MISUSE

The misuse of social media concerns the use of the social media for purposes different from which they have been originally designed, as, for example, for harmful purposes

Just as software, social-networking platforms, and other digital media originally designed for consumer applications may be redeployed for political mobilization, innovations developed for cyber-crime are often used for malicious political activity³ (...) Just as disparate human-rights groups identify with various umbrella causes to which they belong through their immersion in social-networking services and chat platforms, so too do jihadists and militants mobilize around a common “imagined community” that is nurtured online.⁴

The most frequent misuses of social media include actions such as misrepresentation, propaganda, the spread of rumours, and their use for surveillance and censorship purposes. In the context of crisis situations, this translates into easier and faster ways of publishing misleading information through social media, the use of more sophisticated tools for propaganda by authorities in order to gain or maintain reputation during a crisis.

Increasingly, misuse of ICTs in general and social media in particular also includes the use of electronic surveillance, also named as dataveillance, through the collection of information about Internet users without their knowledge, and the utilization of different techniques and technologies to censor, block, or filter information that authorities do not want to be shared during crises.

³ Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, “Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace”, *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.47].

⁴ Ibid., p. 48.

2.2.1. Misrepresentation

Misrepresentation, at its simplest level, concerns the provision of misleading information, or providing a false account about a person, organization or a particular event. This can be done intentionally in order to cause damage to who is being misrepresented for social, economic or political purposes. For example, during a crisis, protesters might be misrepresented by news media and depicted different from what they really are. Often, this is done through the use of examples involving a (typically more extremist) minority of the protestors and causing the public to generalize from the extreme examples to the whole group. Recent research on student protests in the United Kingdom, discussed who mainstream outlets as the BBC and the British newspaper *The Independent*, described the protest as “middle class” as allegedly representative of a whole cohort of students. In this respect, Gokay and Shain have remarked how “The current representation of the protestors as middle class serves a deeply ideological and manipulative function of deflecting attention away from the stark realities of the public cuts and their real causes.”⁵

Misrepresentation can also be unintentional, for instance when an institution or person is identified mistakenly as being responsible for an action or behaviour, as was the case, for example, for Mr. Sunil Tripathi, an innocent man wrongly identified as the bomber in the aftermath of the 15 April 2013 Boston bombings. This case, discussed more widely elsewhere in COSMIC reports,⁶ shows how social media tools such as Reddit were used to propagate information that resulted in the wrongful identification of a person who had nothing to do with the event as the culprit, causing distress to his family and raising questions about how to prevent the dissemination such information on social media, especially if it fits into a narrative that people may want to believe.⁷ This story is important because it shows how a name that had not been pronounced at any time by Boston Police in its communications, but born of out a speculation of a person who had attended High School with Tripathi, and had allegedly recognised him from a surveillance photo, become viral on Reddit, then on other social media networks. The excitement of Reddit users and social media enthusiasts, and the larger public, to find the perpetrators of the bombings was arguably the main cause of rushing to conclusion not based on factual evidence.

2.2.2. Propaganda

New media have also become another platform for authoritarian regimes to spread ‘state propaganda’ by using state-run news sites and web forums, where “the state has used these new features to fine-tune its ideological message, crafting a political environment that sets the tone for online behaviour.”⁸ In this way, states can engage in the adverse use of social media in crisis situations, by providing a platform to support its own position, “a subtler means of influencing the ideological environment than the blunt instrument of official rhetoric.”⁹ For

⁵ Gokay, Bulent, and Farzana, Shain, “Higher Education cuts, Student Protests and Media Misrepresentation”, *Radical Notes*, 23 January 2011, retrieved from <http://radicalnotes.com/2011/01/>

⁶ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013, pp.22-23.

⁷ Madrigal, Alexis, C., “It Wasn't Sunil Tripathi: The Anatomy of a Misinformation Disaster”, *The Atlantic*, 19 April 2013. <http://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2013/04/it-wasnt-sunil-tripathi-the-anatomy-of-a-misinformation-disaster/275155/>

⁸ Kalathil, Shanti, and Taylor C. Boas, *Open Network. Closed Regimes. The Impact of Internet on Authoritarian Rule*, Carnegie Endowment for International Peace, Washington DC, 2003, p.140

⁹ *Ibid.*, p.140

example, as Shanti and Boas have reported in their study of the Internet’s impact on authoritarian rules:

In China, the government has used the online versions of its official newspapers to project a more engaged, inviting image than it does in print publications. Chat rooms featured on the web site of the official People’s Daily, for instance, allow users to vent nationalistic feelings that support the regime’s position on a number of international issues. Essentially, the state can provide these forums for Internet users to support its positions, which is a subtler means of influencing the ideological environment than the blunt instrument of official rhetoric.¹⁰

As discussed elsewhere in COSMIC reports, social media can also be a breeding ground for dissemination of false information for propaganda purposes by groups engaged in “cyber-terrorism.”¹¹ Such use of social media and the Internet for propaganda by terrorist groups may serve several purposes including, but not limited to, increasing the sense of anxiety in the public, recruiting members from marginalized groups within the society by emphasizing injustice, incite further terrorist activities, and even to finance terrorism.¹²

2.2.3. Rumours

A related harmful and adverse use of social media is the spreading of rumours, for instance by targeting a particular person or organization, in order to gain an advantage from a momentarily or long-term loss of reputation by another person or organization.

Basically, rumors are public communications, usually embellished by allegations or attributions based on circumstantial evidence, that reflect people’s assumptions or suspicions about how the world works (Rosnow, 1988)¹³ (...) According to their basic law of rumor, rumors are set in motion when the story is perceived by both the speaker and the listener as important and the true facts are shrouded in ambiguity.¹⁴

As the quote above suggests, rumours are placed within a context where they have a chance to be credible as they fit with pre-existent assumptions or suspicions. The consequences caused by rumours can be quite harmful. As Bordia and DiFonzo remark “They fuel intergroup conflict during war and riots, play havoc with the reputations of companies and products, and cause price swings in the stock market.”¹⁵

A landmark example of the last kind is the episode occurred on 23 April 2013, when a single, fake, tweet, posted on the Associated Press official Twitter account,¹⁶ announcing that there were explosions at the White House, which injured President Obama, resulted in the Dow Jones Index losing 140 points instantly (Figure 1). In practice, this meant that in the space of the three minutes following this tweet an estimated 136.5 million US dollars were wiped out

¹⁰ Ibid., p.140

¹¹ Kotsiopoulos et al., 2013, p.34

¹² United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, “The Use of the Internet for Terrorist Purposes”, 2012, http://www.unodc.org/documents/frontpage/Use_of_Internet_for_Terrorist_Purposes.pdf

¹³ Bordia, Prashant, and Ralph L. Rosnow, “Rumor Rest Stops on the Information Highway Transmission Patterns in a Computer- Mediated Rumor Chain”, *Human Communication Research*, Vol.25, Issue 2, December 1998, pp.163-179 [p.163] - Cited reference: Rosnow, Ralph L., ‘Rumor as communication: A contextualist approach’, *Journal of Communication*, 38, 1988, pp. 12-28.

¹⁴ Ibid., pp.163-4

¹⁵ Bordia, Prashant, and Nicholas DiFonzo, “Problem Solving in Social Interactions on the Internet: Rumor as Social Cognition”, *Social Psychology Quarterly*, Vol. 67, Issue 1, March 2004, pp.33-49 [p.33].

¹⁶ <https://twitter.com/AP>

from the financial value of the index until it was clear that the account had been hacked and the information was not true.¹⁷

Figure 1: A screenshot of the Twitter post on the hacked AP account

Even though the error was corrected moments later, over 4,000 retweets continued to exist on Twitter on other accounts of users who did not rectify the information as AP did as soon as it could. Consequently, although the main Twitter account involved in this story (the account of AP) was edited and corrected, the false information spread on other accounts would be still stored there, prone to be still believed by those who might have not learnt about the hacking action.

As NBC’s columnist Bob Sullivan commented right after the hack attack, rumors spread via Twitter can produce a substantial impact:

It's just the latest sign that lies now spread on the Internet as fast as computer viruses, and can have just as much impact. Like the false rumors that spread like wildfire during the Boston bombing aftermath, or Hurricane Sandy before that, Twitter's surge to mainstream popularity — it now boasts 140 million U.S. accounts — has made it an incredible source of on-the-spot information, but also the world's most powerful rumor-mongering tool.^{18 19}

For crisis managers, this means that they need to be able to react in much faster turnaround than before in order to limit the social, political and economic consequence of rumours spread via social media.

However, the benefit of the existence of social media in the case of rumours is that they can be used to prompt users to verify information as “the online community tends to question rumors more compared to verified news, a pattern which can possibly lead to the

¹⁷ Foster, Peter “‘Bogus’ AP tweet about explosion at the White House wipes billions off US markets”, *The Telegraph*, 23 April 2013, retrieved from <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/finance/markets/10013768/Bogus-AP-tweet-about-explosion-at-the-White-House-wipes-billions-off-US-markets.html>

¹⁸ Sullivan, Bob, “Fake tweet shows country 'sensitive to any news that sounds like terrorism’”, *NBC News*, 23 April 2013, retrieved from: <http://www.nbcnews.com/technology/fake-tweet-shows-country-sensitive-any-news-sounds-terrorism-6C9566725>

¹⁹ For a detailed analysis of Hurricane Sandy’s case study, see Gupta, Aditi et al., “Faking Sandy: Characterizing and Identifying Fake Images on Twitter during Hurricane Sandy”, *International World Wide Web Conference 2013*, and, for a selection of fake pictures, <http://news.yahoo.com/10-fake-photos-hurricane-sandy-075500934.html>

identification of rumours through an aggregate analysis of the data collected.”²⁰ In fact, as discussed more extensively in the Deliverable 2.2 of COSMIC, this is a very important and increasingly used feature in crisis management. For example, the US-based Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA), which co-ordinated the government response to disaster relief efforts of Hurricane Sandy in October 2012, set up a specific page to deal with the spreading rumours and false information and engage the public,²¹ although the success of the initiative was not clearly found out.²²

2.2.4. Surveillance and Censorship

The observation of people’s behaviour is not a characteristic that has emerged with information technologies, but surely ICTs have made it possible to enact surveillance on a greater scale than in the past, thereby making it much easier to collect massive quantities of personal data in digital format. This has led to the claim that we are living in a “surveillance society”²³ where there is an increase of both the amount of surveillance taking place as well as the means to do so. As discussed more widely in the context of the COSMIC deliverable 3.2.1, in the context of crisis management, this also meant that, for example, the “Data retention for secondary use following a crisis can also be seen to be problematic in terms of threatening a person’s privacy when collected and stored for intelligence purposes, thereby being a form of surveillance; data surveillance, otherwise referred to as dataveillance.”²⁴ This has been defined by Clark, as a technique involving “the systematic use of personal data systems in the investigation or monitoring of the actions or communications of one or more persons.”²⁵

Such a context has prompted civil rights activists, columnists, experts and the academic researchers to ask whether technologies that have been promoted for their empowering potential have become predominantly technologies of control. In other words, is the use of GPS-based services in social media applications, which is very useful to help responders to deal with crises more promptly and efficiently open to abuse in the use of their personal data?

Even in democratic countries, surveillance systems penetrate every aspect of life, as people implicitly (and perhaps unwittingly) consent to the greatest invasion of personal privacy in history. Digital information can be easily tracked and raced, and then tied to specific individuals who themselves can be mapped in space and time with a degree of sophistication that would make the greatest tyrants of days past envious. So, are these technologies of freedom or are they technologies of control?²⁶

²⁰ Aman, Hina, Irani Pourang and Hai-Ning Liang, “A Review of Information Communication Technology Applied on Common Tasks during Times of Emergency”, *Proceedings of the 9th International ISCRAM Conference*, 2012, pp.1-10 [p.1]. - Cited reference: Mendoza, M., B. Poblete, et al. ‘Twitter Under Crisis: Can we trust what we RT?’ 1st Workshop on Social Media Analytics (SOMA ’10). 2010

²¹ Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) “Hurricane Sandy: Rumor Control”, 2012, *Federal Emergency Management Agency*, retrieved from <http://www.fema.gov/hurricane-sandy-rumor-control>

²² Papadimitriou, Alex et al., “Deliverable 2.2: Case studies of communication media and their use in crisis situations”, *COSMIC*, 2013, p.45.

²³ Lyon, David (2001) *Surveillance Society: Monitoring Everyday Life*, Open University Press: Buckingham

²⁴ Kotsiopoulos, Alex et al., “Deliverable 3.2.1: Political, social and industrial opportunities arising from the use of emerging technologies”, *COSMIC*, 2013, p.30

²⁵ Roger Clarke, “Introduction to Dataveillance and Information Privacy, and Definitions of Terms”, *Xamax Consultancy*, Aug 1997. <http://www.rogerclarke.com/DV/Intro.html>

²⁶ Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, “Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace”, *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.44]

In fact, the developments following the revelations on the surveillance systems put in place by the US-based National Security Agency (NSA), revealed by former NSA subcontractor Edward Snowden and published by *The Guardian* and *The Washington Post*, have shown the depth by which the agency was able “to access information stored by major US technology companies, often without individual warrants, as well as mass-intercepting data from the fibre-optic cables which make up the backbone of global phone and internet networks” and “undermine the security standards upon which the internet, commerce and banking rely.”²⁷

The (former) top-secret program PRISM had the objective to offer to the NSA, and to the British spy agency GCHQ, “access to information on its targets from the servers of some of the USA’s biggest technology companies: Google, Apple, Microsoft, Facebook, AOL, PalTalk and Yahoo.”²⁸ In other words, the NSA’s use of surveillance tactics can be interpreted as a misuse itself, particularly given the scale of data that service providers have been obliged to pass to the agency without any knowledge of the end users of such services, including popular e-mail and social network platforms.

Such a context does then raises serious questions about the security levels for citizens’ communications, who have been now made aware of the depths and scale of surveillance controls exercised by governmental agencies on the grounds of safety and national security reasons. Security officials have been keen to defend firmly their position on this matter and repeating that Snowden, by revealing sensitive information has done an “enormous disservice to our country” [the US]²⁹, a view shared by officials in the United Kingdom.³⁰

Related to surveillance is the practice of censorship, and current technologies allow both censorship at a systemic (national/international) level, by enacting partial or total closure of networks, as well as the ability to focus attention on specific individual actors that are seen a threat for government authorities.

Indeed, if governments are unable to block content from being viewed, they act by censoring individuals: “Authoritarian states do this most often, and in many cases, with more severity. Bloggers, journalists, and social activists are the most common individual targets of offline censorship, often facing arrests and fines”,³¹ as, for example was the case for an Egyptian student Abdel Kaarem Nabil, a blogger who was sentenced to 4 years in prison in 2007 for allegedly insulting the then Egyptian President Hosni Mubarak and insulting Islam.³²

²⁷ The NSA files’ Edward Snowden: the whistleblower behind the NSA surveillance revelations’, *The Guardian*, 2013, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/world/the-nsa-files>

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Rory Carol, “White House rejects clemency for Edward Snowden over NSA leaks”, *The Guardian*, 3 November 2013, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/nov/03/white-house-nsa-edward-snowden-clemency>

³⁰ Wintour, Patrick, “NSA leaks: UK enemies are ‘rubbing their hands with glee’ says MI6 chief”, *The Guardian*, 8 November 2013, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/nov/07/nsa-leaks-enemies-rubbing-hands-glee-mi6>

³¹ Howard, Philip N., Sheetal D. Agarwal and Muzammil M. Hussain, “When do States Disconnect Their Digital Networks? Regime Responses to the Political Uses of Social Media”, *The Communication Review*, Vol.14, Issue 3, September 2011, pp.216-232 [p. 225]

³² “Egyptian blogger jailed for insulting Islam”, *The Guardian*, 22 February 2007, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2007/feb/22/egypt blogging>

2.2.5. Lateral Surveillance

Among the many aspects of surveillance that Mark Andrejevic has extensively discussed is “lateral surveillance,”³³ within which peers watch each other by combining modern forms of monitoring with traditional methods (e.g. “neighbourhood watch,” especially in case of terrorism) or more recent methods made available by current media technologies, to check on “romantic interests, family, and friends or acquaintances”, and this includes “several levels of monitoring, ranging from casually Googling a new acquaintance to purchasing keystroke monitoring software, surveillance cameras, or even portable lie detectors.”³⁴

Andrejevic argues “with increasing rapidity, technology once restricted to the realm of large corporations and law enforcement organizations is flowing into the hands of individual consumers.”³⁵ The practical consequence of the availability of such technologies, Andrejevic claims, is far from the democratizing (of watching and being watched) potential of new technologies, but rather “the injunction to embrace the strategies of law enforcement and marketing at a micro-level.”³⁶ In other words, online monitoring tools have extended their reach to the “everyday spaces of our homes and offices, from law enforcement and espionage to dating, parenting, and social life,”³⁷ turning every individual into a potential suspect and a spy at the same time. This fuels a general culture of insecurity and suspicion that feeds into and sustains techniques of surveillance, and contributes to dissolve the boundaries between public and private.³⁸

In such a context, the potential of adverse use of new media technologies by end users of online service is much greater than in the past, and carries risks for instance, that can put any targeted person at risk of breach of privacy or being pointed at as a suspect in situations of crisis. Moreover, as discussed earlier in this report with respect to the use of social media by citizens in aftermath of the 2013 Boston bombings, lateral surveillance (e.g., in the form of using and sharing CCTV footage etc., to identify the bombers) may also result in attention to particular racial or ethnic groups in ways that reproduce stereotypes.

2.3. PLAYERS INVOLVED IN MISUSE

After having described the types of misuse, this section will focus on the players that are involved in the misuse of new media. A first distinction can be done between those who do misuse new media—henceforth the misusers—and those who respond to misuse of new media—henceforth the responders.

However, this distinction might not always be clear-cut as players can be both misusers and responders, depending on the circumstances. For example, as it will be seen in subsequent sections, hackers are known for both hacking illegally into systems and accessing unauthorized data, but can also act to make private corporations and governmental authorities more accountable for their actions, most famously with the case of Wikileaks.

³³ Andrejevic, Mark, “The Work of Watching One Another: Lateral Surveillance, Risk and Governance”, *Surveillance and Society*, Vol. 2, Issue 4, 2004, pp.479-497.

³⁴ *Ibid.*, pp.487-488

³⁵ *Ibid.*, p.493

³⁶ *Ibid.*, p.494

³⁷ *Ibid.*, p.494

³⁸ Siapera, Eugenia (2012) *Understanding New Media*, London: Sage, p.109

Governmental authorities, depending on degree of authoritarianism present in a particular country, can also help prevent misuse. They can also misuse the tools offered by new media technologies themselves, for example when higher surveillance systems are put in place to prevent misuses. However, the latter can also lead to abuses of the system, as the NSA case has shown.

For the purposes of this report, we will focus on four main players:

- Hackers
- Scammers
- Government authorities (at international, national and/or local level),
- Private corporations

2.3.1. Hackers

Hacking has usually been used to describe individuals with malicious aims, defined as “a person who uses computers to gain unauthorized access to data.” However, a hacker can also be described as “an enthusiastic and skilful computer programmer or user”³⁹ which can also use such skills for the purposes of exposing fallacies in information systems.

The latter is named as an “ethical hacker,” in other words, “a person who hacks into a computer network in order to test or evaluate its security, rather than with malicious or criminal intent.”⁴⁰ These kinds of hackers also name themselves as ‘hacktivists’, hackers with a cause,⁴¹ who “use rhetoric to try to establish them as politically conscious fighters for the little guy,” but have the problem that “corporations and governments try to frame the hacker as an unproductive, if not destructive, menace to society.”⁴² This leads to efforts to differentiate themselves from malicious hackers, remarking that they are a group of “human rights workers, artists and others who seek to further the goals of human rights through technology.”⁴³

In this view, hacking is seen as a tool to make corporations and governments more accountable for their actions

hacking ... must not be done for its own sake (still less for personal gain) but in order to undermine the information systems of economic and political power. Subversion can occur both outside the law but also within it, by exploiting ambivalences within the law and/or by encouraging the legal apparatus to catch up with developments in ICT, a time lag that governments and corporations are often able to exploit for undesirable ends.⁴⁴

³⁹ ‘Hacker’, Oxford Dictionaries, retrieved from http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/american_english/hacker

⁴⁰ ‘Ethical Hacker’, Oxford Dictionaries, retrieved from http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/american_english/ethical-hacker

⁴¹ Still, Brian, ‘Hacking for a cause’, *Still Monday*, Vol.10, Issue (9), 5 September 2005, retrieved from <http://firstmonday.org/ojs/index.php/fm/article/view/1274/1194>

⁴² Ibid.

⁴³ See <http://www.hacktivismo.com>

⁴⁴ Fitzpatrick, Tony, “Critical Theory, Information Society and Surveillance Technologies”, *Information, Communication & Society*, Vol.5, Issue 3, 2002, pp.357-378 [p.367-8].

During the Arab Spring, for example, networks such as Anonymous⁴⁵ and Hacktivism⁴⁶ “attacked government websites, relayed antigovernment information, and provided fax bridges to enable news to spread despite online censorship (...) When governments blocked and censored opposition websites, Internet hosts were moved to other countries”⁴⁷. In Turkey, RedHack⁴⁸ has been also targeting a number of Ministries and central administration website and exposing what they believe is a misbehaviour by a public authority⁴⁹. However, governments have not stayed reacted to such initiatives and have, directly or indirectly, engaged in supporting groups that engage in what has been defined “patriotic hacking”:

One unusual and important characteristic of cyberspace is that individuals can take creative actions—sometimes against perceived threats to their country’s national interest—that have systemwide effects. Citizens may bristle at outside interference in their country’s internal affairs or take offense at criticism directed at their governments, however illegitimate those governments may appear to outsiders. Those individuals who possess the necessary technical skills have at times taken it upon themselves to attack adversarial sources of information, often leaving provocative messages and warnings behind.⁵⁰

Such episodes have been allegedly quite frequent in cases of political tensions between the Russian Federation and some of its neighbouring countries as Georgia, Estonia, Ukraine and Kyrgyzstan,⁵¹ showing an increasing of adverse use of ICTs in the so-called “cyberwarfare.”

It is important to point out here that the literature review for this report does not reveal substantial evidence of hactivism initiatives outside political crises, or what can become political crises (e.g. the mismanagement of disaster relief efforts by governmental authorities.

As for the methods used in cyberwarfare contexts, these can include Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks and DNS (Domain Name Service) attacks. The DDoS results in the attacked website being flooded by a high number of requests with the help of ‘zombie’ computers that have been previously infected. The DNS attack, instead separates the domain

⁴⁵ “A name that refers to groups of people who disrupt the Internet to play pranks or as a means of protest. (...) associated with high-profile cyber attacks on companies and government agencies. With no clear leadership structure or rules of membership, it exists as a fluid collective of people”. Olson, Parmy *We Are Anonymous: Inside the Hacker World of LulzSec, Anonymous, and the Global Cyber Insurgency*. New York: Little Brown and Company, 2012

⁴⁶ Hacktivism practitioners describe themselves as “a group of international hackers, human rights workers, artists and others who seek to further the goals of human rights through technology (...) committed to developing technologies in support of the highest standards of human rights”.

See <http://www.hacktivism.com/news/>

⁴⁷ Allagui, Ilhem, and Johanne Kuebler, “The Arab Spring and the role of ICTs”, *International Journal of Communication*, Vol.5, 2011, pp.1435-1442 [p.1436].

⁴⁸ “Redhack claims to be affiliated with the international hackers’ group Anonymous group, and has carried out several online attacks against state and private domains [in Turkey] since 1997”. AFP, ‘Hackers’ on trial in Turkey for the First Time, *Al Arabiya*, 26 November 2012, retrieved from <http://english.alarabiya.net/articles/2012/11/26/251896.html>

⁴⁹ See <http://redhack.tumblr.com/> The blog includes also the transcription of an interview to an alleged RedHack activist (“EXCLUSIVE interview with RedHack on Halk TV regarding #occupygezi #occupyturkey and in general”)

⁵⁰ Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, “Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace”, *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.53-4].

⁵¹ Ibid.

address (e.g. www.bbc.com) from its numerical address (e.g. 192.100.200.100), which prevents users to access the site until the two are linked again⁵².

In the case of the conflict between Russia and Georgia in 2008,⁵³ attacks towards Georgia were reported in the form of DDoS, allegedly from Russia, which shut down servers in Georgia, including the president's website, media and communication sites and the website of the National Bank of Georgia.⁵⁴ Allegedly, Russian nationalists were also behind the DDoS attack that put offline the servers in Kyrgyzstan.⁵⁵ In 2009, during the campaign for the 12 June presidential elections in Iran, a group that was known as the Iranian Cyber Army replaced the home pages of opposition websites with their own texts and took over a number of Twitter accounts. As Deibert and Rohozinski stated, "Although no formal connection to the Iranian authorities has been established, the groups responsible for the attacks posted pro-regime messages on the hacked websites and services".⁵⁶ This shows how regimes have been adapting not only at policing but also at using hacking techniques to spread misinformation and propaganda in times of political crises, and trying to silence the voices of opposition movements not only in physical squares, but also in virtual public spaces.

This discussion regarding hacktivism and patriotic hacking illustrates the possibility of an "escalation and/or spill over of conflict into cyberspace,"⁵⁷ an adverse use of media that is likely to increase in situations of crisis, as the development of technologies makes it possible to conduct attacks on a large scale through the participation of like-minded hackers.

2.3.2. Scammers

Unlike hackers, scammers have no related positive connotations related to their activities, which are simply engaging in fraud or dishonest behaviour. As the Merriam-Webster Dictionary defines them a scammer is "a dishonest person who uses clever means to cheat others out of something of value."⁵⁸ More specifically, in the context of crises, scamming can practically involve using those means to collect money, and making trustful users believe that such funds are being destined to disaster relief rather than, in reality, being pocketed by electronic thieves.

The development of information technologies has contributed to the growth in the extent and the sophistication of such activities

⁵² Karatzogianni, Athina, "The Politics of Cyberconflict", *Journal of Politics*, Vol.24, Issue 1, 2004, pp.46-55

⁵³ On 7 August 2008 Georgian military forces responded to attacks by secessionists in the ethnic enclave of South Ossetia by targeting the region's capital, Tskhinvali. In the following five days the Georgian army tried to retake the territory but the Russian Federation, supportive of the South Ossetians, responded with an invasion and by targeting key military objectives within Georgia. See also King, Charles, "The Five Day War. Managing Moscow after the Georgia Crisis", November-December 2013, retrieved from: <http://www.foreignaffairs.com/articles/64602/charles-king/the-five-day-war>.

⁵⁴ Markoff, John, "Before the Gunfire. Cyberattacks", *The New York Times*, 2008, retrieved from http://www.nytimes.com/2008/08/13/technology/13cyber.html?_r=0

⁵⁵ Googin, Gerard, "The Models and Politics of Mobile Media", *Fiberculture*, 2008, retrieved from <http://twelve.fiberculturejournal.org/fcj-082-the-models-and-politics-of-mobile-media/>

⁵⁶ Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, "Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace", *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.54].

⁵⁷ Siapera, Eugenia *Understanding New Media*, London: Sage, 2012, p.113

⁵⁸ "Scammer", *Free Merriam-Webster Dictionary*, 2013, retrieved from: <http://www.merriam-webster.com/thesaurus/scammer>

Although most cyber-crime takes the form of petty spam (the electronic distribution of unsolicited bulk messages), the sophistication and reach of cyber-criminals today are startling. The production of “malware”—malicious software—is now estimated to exceed that of legitimate software, although no one really knows its full extent. About a million new malware samples a month are discovered by security engineers, with the rate of growth increasing.⁵⁹ (...) Infiltration of adversarial networks through targeted “social malware” (software designed to infiltrate an unsuspecting user’s computer) and “drive-by” Web exploits (websites infected with viruses that target insecure browsers) is exploding throughout the dark underbelly of the Internet.⁶⁰

Cugelman et al. (2009), in their review of website credibility, also outlined how “one study of online scams found that 90 percent of participants (including technical experts) could not differentiate between legitimate and criminal Web sites” (Dhamija et al. 2006).⁶¹ Recent data about the extent of the phenomenon “indicate that victims lose around €290 billion each year worldwide as a result of cybercriminal activities,” prompting the European Commission to open an European Cybercrime Center.⁶² A 2012 Eurobarometer did also highlight how “Europeans remain very concerned about cyber security. 89% of internet users avoid disclosing personal information online, and 12% have already experienced online fraud.”⁶³

With the increase of sophistication of the available platforms to enact identity theft, phishing and spam, this is also an area that is likely to rise and that can lead to problematic situations during emergencies. For example, fundraising campaigns that are organized after a disaster and/or during a crisis can include scammers that can get the attention of internet users and channel funds that end up supporting online crime rather than the charitable activity a user would have been looking for.

As reported in detail elsewhere in COSMIC⁶⁴, in the case of 2010 Haiti Earthquake, social media were also used to set up bogus donations websites that mushroomed in the aftermath of the disaster event, and managing to gather over 1,5 million members before getting disabled by Facebook’s staff.⁶⁵ Two years later following Hurricane Sandy in 2012, in the USA, similar issues were also presented,⁶⁶ with a reported 1,000 websites registered with the words “Sandy”, “relief” even before the storm hit New Jersey and continuing to operate also in reconstruction phase following the disaster.⁶⁷ In earlier disasters including Hurricane Katrina in the US, such scams are estimated to have “consumed between \$300,000 to \$400,000 of Red Cross donations” prompting the creation of a Hurricane Katrina Fraud Task Force in the U.S.⁶⁸

⁵⁹ Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, “Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace”, *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.46].

⁶⁰ Ibid. p.54

⁶¹ Cugelman, Brian, Mike Thelwall and Phil Dawes, “The Dimensions of Web Site Credibility and Their Relation to Active Trust and Behavioural Impact”, *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, Vol. 24, Article 26, March 2009, pp.455-472 [p.462].

⁶² Malmstrom Cecilia, ‘Opening of European Cybercrime Centre’, *European Commission*, 9 January 2013, retrieved from http://ec.europa.eu/commission_2010-2014/malmstrom/news/archives/2013/01/20130109_en.htm

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., p.58-59

⁶⁵ Sullivan, Bob “Facebook full of fake Haiti fundraisers”, *NBC News Technology*, 18 January 2010, retrieved from <http://www.nbcnews.com/technology/facebook-full-fake-haiti-fundraisers-6C10406415>

⁶⁶ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., p.45

⁶⁷ Kircheimer, Sid, “Beware of Hurricane Sandy Scams”, 19 November 2012, retrieved from <http://www.aarp.org/money/scams-fraud/info-11-2012/hurricane-sandy-scams.html>

⁶⁸ Gerson, Danielle, “Haiti needs help, swindlers on standby”, *NPR.com*, 15 January 2010, retrieved from http://www.npr.org/blogs/tellmemore/2010/01/haiti_needs_help_swindlers_on.html

Then, in such a context, it is important to point out how, especially in the phases preceding and following crises caused by natural disasters, it is crucial that agencies have effective tools to counteract the possible interception of legitimate funds for illegitimate purposes and keep the public informed about the ways of supporting disaster relief and the organizations that are really involved in those operations. This can include purposely made websites and databases that can be consulted online, as well as the activation of phone hotlines that help to prevent fraud.⁶⁹

2.3.3. Government Authorities

According to Howard et al, there are two main reasons that would prompt governments to enact measures to prevent what they believe to be a misuse of the media and communication systems: 1) protecting political authority and 2) preserving the public good. Protecting political authority includes “protecting political leaders and state institutions; election crisis; eliminating propaganda; mitigating dissidence; and national security.” Preserving the public good, instead, aims at “preserving cultural and religious morals; preserving racial harmony; protecting children; cultural preservation; protecting individuals’ privacy; and dissuading criminal activity.”⁷⁰

It should be noted that the interpretation of the reasons that would prompt governments to “protect” their political authority and public good can very much vary according to the kind of government that is in place in a particular country at a particular time, something that will be better illustrated by the examples outlined later in this report.

From controlling national telecommunication infrastructures to designing and enacting related policies, from offering e-government solutions to using the same infrastructure to control the online activities of its citizens, government authorities are arguably the most important player in the use and misuse of media.

Later in this report, the section on Managing and Mismanaging Misuse will discuss in more detail governments’ role in managing external and internal threats originating by an alleged misuse of the ICTs by those subjects whose interests contrast with government authorities’ priorities. It is important to indicate that due to the relative weakness of supranational organizations that are involved in communications and telecommunications policy, national governments are still, and will probably continue to be for the foreseeable future the reference player in this context.

Governments can, in fact, also influence the decisions of new media companies that operate or are based within their national territory. In the case of Turkey, for example, the government, reportedly “to prevent a repeat of Gezi-like incidents” given that “social media played a key role during the protests given the fact that most of the groups organized and communicated through social media platforms such as Twitter and Facebook” decided to put in place stricter mechanisms of surveillance on social media networks after the Gezi Park

⁶⁹ Federal Bureau of Investigation, “Justice Department Officials Raise Awareness Of Disaster Fraud Hotline”, 1 November 2012, retrieved from <http://www.fbi.gov/news/pressrel/press-releases/justice-department-officials-raise-awareness-of-disaster-fraud-hotline>

⁷⁰ Ibid., pp. 226-7.

demonstrations that took place in June 2013.⁷¹ During the protests Facebook denied the claim that it had cooperated with the Turkish Government and shared any user data with it, following a claim to the contrary made by the Turkish Minister of Transport, Binali Yildirim.⁷²

As recent events like the aforementioned NSA/Snowden leak seem to suggest, some national governments are in fact more powerful than others in imposing terms of pressuring companies to comply with their agenda, and in making a secret and adverse use of the possibilities offered by new media. In fact, the United States are arguably able to exercise more power due to the fact that a high number of popular services (Facebook, Twitter, etc.) and cloud-based applications (Google, Microsoft, file sharing, server space, etc.) are based on its soil, rather than elsewhere.

Indeed, the degree of real ‘internationalization’ of the Internet has been a concern of communication policy activists and researchers that claim that “non-US needs, preferences and perspectives have not been adequately taken into account” in the Internet governance and public interest discussions.⁷³

Although critics of the way the US administration interacts with new media companies based in the country have been present much before the recent events following Snowden’s revelations, the scale of the facts revealed about NSA surveillance program has produced discussions that may potentially have significant long-term consequences. As The Observer’s John Naughton commented,

no US-based internet company can be trusted to protect our privacy or data. The fact is that Google, Facebook, Yahoo, Amazon, Apple and Microsoft are all integral components of the US cyber-surveillance system. Nothing, but nothing, that is stored in their "cloud" services can be guaranteed to be safe from surveillance or from illicit downloading by employees of the consultancies employed by the NSA.⁷⁴

2.3.4. Private Corporations

The misuse of new media technologies by corporations during times of crisis includes the attempt to gain media exposure by piggybacking on an unfolding crisis event and use it for marketing and public relations purposes by attracting more visitors to their own website or social media accounts.

A recent case has been the misuse of e-mail mass marketing by the US-based clothing manufacturer American Apparel at the time Hurricane Sandy hit the US East Coast on 30th October 2012 (Figure 2). The corporation sent a mass message to its customers in which

⁷¹ ‘Turkish police, intelligence to actively monitor social media after Gezi’, *Today’s Zaman*, 7 October 2013, retrieved from <http://www.todayszaman.com/news-328412-turkish-police-intelligence-to-actively-monitor-social-media-after-gezi.html>

⁷² ‘Facebook denies report on share of user data with Turkish gov’t amid protests’, *Anadolu Agency*, 26 June 2013, retrieved from <http://www.aa.com.tr/en/s/197809--facebook-denies-report-on-share-of-user-data-with-turkish-govt-amid-protests>

⁷³ Braman, Sandra “Internationalization of the Internet by design: the first decade”, *Global Media and Communication*, Volume 8, Issue 1, April 2012, pp.27-45, [p. 28]. See also “Legal Globalization and Communication Law”, by the same author, *2013 International Communication Association (ICA) Pre-Conference ‘Global Communications and National Policies: The Return of the State?’*, London, 16 June, 2013

⁷⁴ Naughton, John, ‘Edward Snowden’s not the story. The fate of the internet is’, *The Observer*, retrieved from <http://www.guardian.co.uk/technology/2013/jul/28/edward-snowden-death-of-internet>

invited them to an “Hurricane Sandy Sale”, available only in the states hit by the storm, for the following 36 hours, in case they would be “bored during the storm”⁷⁵

Allegedly, this was not the first time that the company used controversial methods, but, not surprisingly, the reaction on social media by customers living in the area hit by the storm was overwhelmingly negative.

Figure 2: American Apparel “Hurricane Sandy Sale”

A related case was also the use of Twitter by fashion designer Kenneth Cole where, in the middle of the political crises in Egypt he tweeted "Millions are in uproar in #Cairo. Rumor is they heard our new spring collection is now available online at <http://bit.ly/KCairo-KC>" causing outraged reactions by Twitter users in the U.S., Egypt as well as by social activists worldwide and resulting in a public apology for his Tweet.⁷⁶

Although such episodes are quite rarely used by private corporations for marketing purposes, they highlight forms of misuses of new media that can be made at little economic cost during times of crises. However, as COSMIC reported in Deliverable 2.2., at times of emergencies, use of social media by companies may often, albeit without malintentions, lead to misinformation. For example, during the UK Heatwave, companies utilized hashtags like #heatwave to advertise sunglasses, ice cream and other goods, decreasing the effectiveness of the utilization of Twitter for information dissemination.⁷⁷

⁷⁵ Li, Anita, “American Apparels angers Twittersphere with Hurricane Sandy Sale”, 30 October 2012, retrieved from <http://mashable.com/2012/10/30/american-apparel-sandy/>

⁷⁶ Ehrlich, Brenna, “Kenneth Cole #Cairo Tweet Angers the Internet”, 3 February 2011, retrieved from <http://mashable.com/2011/02/03/kenneth-cole-egypt/>

⁷⁷ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., 2013, p.33.

Private companies can also become the target of hackers' attention and victims of misuse of new media tools. Particularly in the context of political crises, businesses that allegedly support one of the two sides in a conflict can have their website and/or social media outlets taken offline or hacked. For example, recently, *International Business Times* reports that during the Gezi Park Protests in Turkey (June 2013) the hacker group Anonymous “used distributed denial of service, or DDoS, hacks to overload servers and knock target websites offline. In addition to websites belonging to the Turkish government, political parties and police department, Anonymous hacked websites belonging to media outlets that support Prime Minister Tayyip Erdogan. One example was the private news broadcaster NTV, which was criticized for not reporting on the police brutality.”⁷⁸

Also, as will be discussed in the next section, corporations can also be involved as players in management of/response to misuse.

2.4. MANAGING AND MISMANAGING MISUSE

As our examples from the previous sections have illustrated (e.g., scamming during Hurricane Sandy), during emergencies and crises, misuses of new communication technologies are increasingly more widespread. This section will focus on measures that different stakeholders use or may use to manage/respond to misuse of new communication technologies. Before we do so, we will distinguish between what we will call as management of “internal” and “external” threats.

On the one hand, in most of the situations described above, players will need to manage the emergence of threats that originate from other players. External threats can target governments and organisations, who react to such initiatives by enacting a number of countermeasures that include the limitation or closure of websites and networks. In the following subsection, we will discuss how the potential misuse of new media, particularly during political crises, has also prompted the implementation of increasingly sophisticated levels of surveillance and censorship, to which, private citizens, and specifically activists, have reacted with methods as sousveillance (inverse surveillance) and counter-surveillance.

On the other hand, when a certain misuse of communication technologies originate from within the organization, these threats can be described as “internal”. Internal threats originate from the vast availability of data in digital format which has facilitated the use of such data by person(s) within an organization for the purposes of damaging its reputation, make a sensible set of data available to those that want to harm an organization, or make a particular kind of information known to the larger public. This will be discussed in the final subsection of this section, where it will be also pointed out how data mining techniques can support the discovery and management of such matters when they arise.

2.4.1. Managing external threats

When confronted with what is believed to be a misuse of information and communication technologies (ICTs) to destabilize or topple a government, states have resorted to measures that would impede the access to a particular media content (a video or audio clip, images, or

⁷⁸ Neal, Ryan W., “#OpTurkey: Anonymous Hacks 145 Turkish Websites And Shares Free Internet Access To Protestors In Turkey”, *International Business Times*, June 04, 2013, retrieved from <http://www.ibtimes.com/opturkey-anonymous-hacks-145-turkish-websites-shares-free-internet-access-protestors-turkey-1290799>

texts), or a specific website or application (YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, among others). More stringent measures include the slowdown of network capacity, often due to additional filtering being in place, or the shutdown of part or of the whole network infrastructure, both landline and mobile.

For instance, during the 2011 protests against the Egyptian Government, which eventually led to the ousting of President Hosni Mubarak, Egyptian authorities shut down the whole network infrastructure in the country with the purpose of containing the expanding protests on the streets. Contrary to their wish, this caused more people to go into streets to find out what was happening, as well as escalating the cyber-conflict to a higher level, and prompted global activists, as the Anonymous network, as well as companies that owned social media platforms as Facebook, Twitter and Google (with YouTube), to share media content originating from Egypt

The unprecedented act of cutting Egypt from the global Internet essentially transformed the Egyptian uprising against the Mubarak regime into a global power struggle between the embattled regime and the international global information and communication technology community (...) These companies became information activists because they had an important stake in the outcome of the Egyptian Revolution—they wanted to maintain their global information technology hegemony in the region.⁷⁹

So what emerged during the events in Egypt was the expansion of players and interests that governments will need to deal with when managing a situation of crisis, something that other governments have since then taken into consideration when responding to political crises. This expanded set of players included a network of local and international activists, global IT companies and, in the background, those players that might, or might not, have an interest in keeping or toppling the Mubarak government in Egypt. As Lyombe and Haman stated

Though the Arab Spring was, strictly speaking, a regional phenomenon of the Arabic-Islamic countries of North Africa and the Middle East, their instrumentalization of the Internet and its associated networked social media as weapons of dictatorship transformed the upheavals into global phenomena. This is because in their attempts to assert hegemony over the Internet and the telecommunications infrastructure, the governments of North Africa posed a threat to the business interests and information technology hegemony of global information technology corporations⁸⁰

This case demonstrated some of the limits of the “hegemonic gateway model of Internet regulation”⁸¹ when a government is the gateway for Internet access for a national territory, controlling, surveilling and filtering access. In the case of Egypt, pulling the plug had very high economic costs and important political consequences, as telecom companies lost significant revenues and the political outcome was actually contrary to what the Mubarak regime had wished for. In fact, in the end, protesters moved from virtual spaces into real streets in order to find out what was happening in the protests, as well as supporting the protests and, toppling the Egyptian Government in February 2011.

⁷⁹ Eko, Lyombe S. and John Haman, “The Internet, State Hegemony versus Corporate Hegemony in the North African Arab Spring”, *63rd Annual Conference of the International Communication Association (ICA)*, London, 2013, pp.1-30 [p.23-24].

⁸⁰ Ibid, p.28. For a more detailed account see also Eko, Lyombe S., *New Media, Old Regimes. Case Studies in Comparative Communication and Policy*, Lexington Books: Lanham MD, 2012

⁸¹ Ibid., p. 12

In order to understand the wider historical and global context of governments' responses, it is also important to perform an analysis that spans over time and regions of the world, and this is what Howard et al. (2011) have attempted in a comparative study that covers sixteen years across a wide range of geographies.⁸² Howard et al. constructed a database of 566 incidents that have highlighted how digital media and social networks have changed the way civil society is organizing dissent: "Social movement leaders from around the world use online applications and digital content systems to organize collective action, activate local protest networks, network with international social movements, and share their political perspective with global media systems."⁸³

When confronting what they have believed to be an adverse use of the media of local civil society actors (often in collaboration with wider global social movements), government authorities have resorted to different actions such as filtering all the incoming and outgoing content at all times ('the Great Wall of China'), or more intensely in particular occasions (Iran presidential elections, 2009), asking technology providers to help them in the surveillance process by making available datasets (Facebook, Twitter, e-mail services) or stop encrypting communications (Blackberry/RIM vs. United Arab Emirates, Saudi Arabia and India, 2010). As discussed earlier in this report, the recent events surrounding the Gezi Park protests in Turkey in Summer 2013 have also shown how a government will be inclined to increase its monitoring of social media by asking outlets such as Twitter and Facebook to share their data with the local authorities.^{84 85}

In such situations, as was the case in China, for Google and Yahoo, leading IT companies may face an uneasy choice between being excluded from a valuable market or having their tools 'adapted' to comply with national restrictions. In other words

In times of political uncertainty, rigged elections, or military incursions, ruling elites are sometimes willing to interfere with information infrastructure as a way of managing crises. In many of these cases, the targets (victims) are active domestic civic society movements with international linkages⁸⁶

Howard et al.'s study also highlights the increasing role of IT in crisis situations when evaluating political response and counterinsurgency tactics⁸⁷ and as a tool for local civil societies to "incubate civic conversations, especially in countries that heavily censor the national print and broadcast media."⁸⁸ This is an outcome more likely to happen in situations of political crises, rather than in the other types, or in political crises following the mismanagement of disaster relief operation in the aftermath of a natural or man-made disaster.

⁸² Howard, Philip N., Sheetal D. Agarwal and Muzammil M. Hussain, "When do States Disconnect Their Digital Networks? Regime Responses to the Political Uses of Social Media", *The Communication Review*, Vol.14, Issue 3, September 2011, pp.216-232

⁸³ Ibid., p.218

⁸⁴ Turkish police, intelligence to actively monitor social media after Gezi', *Today's Zaman*, 7 October 2013, retrieved from <http://www.todayszaman.com/news-328412-turkish-police-intelligence-to-actively-monitor-social-media-after-gezi.html>

⁸⁵ 'Facebook denies report on share of user data with Turkish gov't amid protests', *Anadolu Agency*, 26 June 2013, retrieved from <http://www.aa.com.tr/en/s/197809--facebook-denies-report-on-share-of-user-data-with-turkish-govt-amid-protests>

⁸⁶ Ibid., p.220

⁸⁷ Ibid., p-221

⁸⁸ Ibid., p-230

While filtering schemes represent the first generation of Internet controls, new schemes have emerged in recent years, thank to the development and increased sophistication of IT tools and counterinsurgency techniques. According to Deibert and Rohozinski, second generation types of controls are those that “create a legal and normative environment and technical capabilities that enable actors to deny access to information resources as and when needed,” as in situations of crises involving large demonstrations against a government.⁸⁹ A step further, third generation types of internet controls are those that

take a highly sophisticated, multidimensional approach to enhancing state control over national cyberspace and building capabilities for competing in informational space with potential adversaries and competitors (...) the focus is less on denying access than successfully competing with potential threats through effective counterinformation campaigns that overwhelm, discredit, or demoralize opponents. Third-generation controls also focus on the active use of surveillance and data mining as means to confuse and entrap opponents⁹⁰.

As this section has shown, the levels and degree of sophistication of tools used to respond to what governments may concern as external threats during crises has been growing with the development of technologies and applications that help to process increasing amounts of data in decreasing amount of time. This has also increased concern among activists and civil society organisations about the concentration of power “in the hands of who collect and control surveillance data” as this can be “detrimental to the democratic principles that our societies are said to function.”⁹¹

Finally, as Deibert and Rohozinski have highlighted, the concentration of surveillance data that moves from public to private hands is another serious concern

For governments in both the developed and developing worlds, delegating censorship and surveillance to private companies keeps these controls on the “frontlines” of the networks and coopts the actors who manage the key access points and hosting platforms. If this trend continues, we can expect more censorship and surveillance responsibilities to be carried out by private companies, carrier hotels (ISP co-location centers), cloud-computing services, Internet exchanges, and telecommunications companies. Such a shift in the locus of controls raises serious issues of public accountability and transparency for citizens of all countries.⁹²

2.4.2. Sousveillance and Countersurveillance

Another two concepts related to surveillance are, “sousveillance” (also known as inverse surveillance) and “countersurveillance.” The first concept derives, as surveillance, from the French meaning of the act of watching (veiller) from below (sous). So, opposite to surveillance, in the case of sousveillance “the watchers are socially below those who are watched”⁹³ and was originally promoted by the Canadian researcher and inventor Steve

⁸⁹ Deibert, Ronald, and Rohozinski, Rafal, “Beyond Denial. Introducing Next-Generation Information Access Controls”, in Deibert et al. (eds.) *Access Controlled. The Shaping of Power, Rights and Rule in Cyberspace*, MIT Press: Cambridge MA, 2010, pp.3-13 [p.7]

⁹⁰ Ibid., p.

⁹¹ Siapera, Eugenia *Understanding New Media*, London: Sage, 2012, p.108

⁹² Deibert, Ronald, and Rafal Rohozinski, “Liberation vs. Control. The Future of Cyberspace”, *Journal of Democracy*, Vol. 21, Issue 4, October 2010, pp.43-57 [p.53].

⁹³ Ganascia, Jean-Gabriel “The generalized sousveillance society”, *Social Science Information*, Vol.49, Issue 3, 2010, pp.489-507, [p.493].

Mann⁹⁴. His notion of sousveillance focuses on “enhancing the ability of people to access and collect data about their surveillance and to neutralize surveillance.”⁹⁵ Fitzpatrick argues that this “can mean filming the police who film demonstrations or it can mean using data protection legislation to expose corporate misdemeanours.”⁹⁶

Mann et al. refer to what, at the time of the article, was arguably the most famous example of sousveillance, the videotaping of Los Angeles resident George Holliday that documented the beating of Rodney King, who had been stopped by the police after a traffic violation on 3 March 1991. The broadcast of the recording on TV prompted nationwide discussion on the use of brutality by the police. A year later, on 29 April 1992 the trial jury acquitted the Los Angeles Police Department officers of assault and use of excessive force, and this led to riots and a situation of crisis in the urban area of Los Angeles until 4 May 1992.⁹⁷

The Rodney King case was a coincidence though, and Mann outlines that there are also acts of sousveillance that can be planned as “citizens photographing police officers who come to their doors; civilians photographing government officials; residents beaming satellite shots of occupying troops onto the Internet.”⁹⁸ Sousveillance has the potential not only of “catching” episodes of misconduct by people abusing their position of power, but also to reduce the possibility that such events might happen again in the future because people in position of power would know that they might be “watched” and publicly shared by an increasing number of people who own mobile devices (e.g., smartphones, tablets) with embedded cameras.

Applications for sousveillance purposes include tools as the “Stop and Frisk Watch” used in the city of New York, a smart phone application that claims to empower “New Yorkers to monitor police activity and hold the NYPD accountable for unlawful stop-and-frisk encounters and other police misconduct.”⁹⁹ This way, ordinary citizens have a tool that can support their attempt to make police forces more accountable, especially in context of crisis situations where, in their opinion, their might be a risk of misbehaviour or use of excessive force by law enforcement authorities.

The second concept to be explored here, counter-surveillance, is instead the practice of making surveillance difficult or avoid it altogether, including technologies to avoid cyber-intrusions in or through electronic devices.

The Snowden/NSA case has prompted a wider discussion also on this front, with a considerable number of mainstream media outlets publishing information that would advise readers on methods and techniques to protect or hide their identity online. The New York Magazine, for example, showed Internet users practical examples of using the web anonymously by using encryption technologies for texts and Virtual Private Networks (VPN)

⁹⁴ Mann, Steve, Nolan, Jason. and Wellman, Barry. “Sousveillance: inventing and using wearable computing devices for data collection in surveillance environments”, *Surveillance & society*, Vol.1, Issue 3, 2003, pp.331–55.

⁹⁵ *Ibid.*, p.333

⁹⁶ Fitzpatrick, Tony, “Critical Theory, Information Society and Surveillance Technologies”, *Information, Communication & Society*, Vol.5, Issue 3, 2002, pp.357-378 [p.367].

⁹⁷ Staten, Clark, “Three days of hell in Los Angeles”, *Bibalex archives*, 1992, retrieved from <http://web.archive.bibalex.org/web/20070903160703/http://www.emergency.com/la-riots.htm> .

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*, p.334

⁹⁹ “Activists Create Stop and Frisk Watch Smart Phone App”, *Intellihub* 25 July 2013, retrieved from <http://intellihub.com/2013/07/25/activists-create-stop-and-frisk-watch-smart-phone-app/>

for navigation.¹⁰⁰ The Guardian’s Cory Doctorow also suggested ways of websites to inform users if NSA had compromised their security without risking penalties under US law.¹⁰¹

Such techniques would include the use of apps such as Wickr,¹⁰² and app that allows users to send and receive encrypted communications that would self-destruct shortly after being viewed. Other popular applications include a private VPN (Virtual Private Network) service as HideMyAss¹⁰³ that, through it servers located across the globe, would make a user look as it is logging in from a different country than the real one (e.g., United Kingdom rather than Turkey).

Applications for e-mail might include services as Hushmail,¹⁰⁴ a “privacy-oriented email service with built-in encryption,” and browsers as Tor¹⁰⁵ that help protect from internet surveillance and traffic analysis of the end-user.

Internet activists have also been developing social networks that would cater specifically to those with privacy concerns and are inclined to make a more use of technologies that might anonymize internet traffic, for example, also for journalists working in authoritarian countries.¹⁰⁶

Therefore, especially in the context of political crises, and where the life of professional journalists, and citizen reporters, is potentially at risk when reporting from countries with either higher or lower levels of press freedom, such tools can help to make governmental authorities more accountable, as well as spreading awareness about their actions, to the national and especially the international public.

2.4.3. Managing internal threats

After having discussed the adverse use of information systems that occur due to attacks originating outside a given system, it is also important to discuss another form of misuse that is facilitated by the tools available with new media. In fact, large quantities of information that are available in digital format can be copied and shared in a way that is much easier than in the past, given that all is needed is a valid login and a capable storage disk, rather than the physical relocation of paper and hard copies.

As Calandrino, McKinner and Sheldon point out, insiders

pose the greatest risk to an organization’s information systems. Organizations grant insiders both authorized access to and knowledge of their information systems, primarily computer systems and the organization’s network. In the past, insiders have abused this trust by stealing or corrupting data, committing fraud, and modifying performance reports. Because these

¹⁰⁰ Roose, Kevin. “The Surveillance Free Day”, *New York Magazine*, 29 July 2013, retrieved from <http://nymag.com/daily/intelligencer/2013/07/surveillance-free-day-part-i.html>

¹⁰¹ Doctorow, Cory “How to foil NSA sabotage: use a dead man’s switch”, *The Guardian*, 9 September 2013, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2013/sep/09/nsa-sabotage-dead-mans-switch> [accessed 12 September 2013]

¹⁰² Home Page, *Wickr*, 2013, retrieved from <https://www.mywickr.com/en/index.php>

¹⁰³ Home Page, *HideMyAss*, 2013, retrieved from <http://www.hidemypass.com/>

¹⁰⁴ Home Page. *Hushmail*, 2013, retrieved from <http://www.hushmail.com/>

¹⁰⁵ “Tor: Overview”, *Tor Project*, 2013, retrieved from <https://www.torproject.org/about/overview.html.en>

¹⁰⁶ “Dislike this: social media alternatives”, *10 Tactics Remixed*, 2013, retrieved from <https://informationactivism.org/en/dislike-social-media-alternatives>

insiders may act within the bounds of their privileges, mitigation of the insider threat differs from that of external threats.¹⁰⁷

The fact that insiders are able to access an organization's information system, although often with different set of privileges, depending on their position within the organization, exposes organizations to potential theft and unauthorized (intentional or non-intentional) sharing of confidential information with other person(s) or organization(s). In this view, the outcome of revelations by the kinds of Wikileaks or the NSA/Snowden affair has been framed by the organizations the information was taken from as an element that can add further danger to the public order or national security in the context of political and man-made crises.

In order to mitigate the consequences of such threats, technologies help system administrators detect suspicious and undesirable insider behaviour by the use of data mining tools and the analysis of access patterns, alerting them when deviations from such patterns occur.

Such data mining tools include the use of the Local Outlier Factor (LOF) and its score as a point of reference.¹⁰⁸ The threshold for each system can be set at different levels by system administrators and, according to Calandrino et al. (2007) this technology can accommodate some flexibility in order to take in consideration anomaly scores of users, the elimination of false positives and ignore "certain LOF scores heavily influenced by attributes that the administrator considers insignificant."¹⁰⁹ Where techniques to detect suspicious insiders behaviour might differ, they share the fact that they compare the behaviour of a particular user to a set of data that includes their history and behaviour within the organization network.¹¹⁰

In the context of crisis situations such systems can help to minimise the possible consequences of misuse of new media for the purposes of creating harm to an organization and alert the relevant authorities or managers about possible situations of threat.

As such, institutions that deal particularly with matters of national safety, military and police operations and intelligence, can be particular exposed in times of crises to the insider threat of personnel that is able to access highly confidential information, resulting possibly also in financial losses. For example, as a report of US Department of Defense (DoD) has stated

A DoD employee obtained an encrypted password file from a DoD classified network and decoded the password file at home, subsequently gaining unlimited access to the classified network, disruption on normal operations and the theft of DoD information resulting in a \$4.78 million loss to the government.¹¹¹

Such episodes illustrate the possible consequences of the misuse of new media posed by internal threats that have to be taken into account as potential risk in crisis situations, and the necessity of have tools as the LOF to detect such events at an early stage.

¹⁰⁷ Calandrino, Joseph A., Steven J. McKinney, and Frederick T. Sheldon, "Detection of Undesirable Insider Behavior", *Cyber Security and Information Workshop*, 2007, pp.1-4 [p.1].

¹⁰⁸ For a detailed account of the LOF, see M. M. Breunig, H.-P. Kriegel, R. T. Ng, J. Sander. "LOF: Identifying density-based local outliers", *Proceedings of the ACM SIGMOD 2000 International Conference on Management of Data*, ACM, 2000

¹⁰⁹ Calandrino, Joseph A., Steven J. McKinney, and Frederick T. Sheldon, "Detection of Undesirable Insider Behavior", *Cyber Security and Information Workshop*, 2007, pp.1-4 [p.3].

¹¹⁰ For a detailed account see Wolff, Matt, "Unsupervised Methods of Detecting a Malicious Insider", *Proceedings of the 7th International ISCRAM Conference*, 2010, p.1-2.

¹¹¹ Department of Defense, "Final Report of the Insider Threat Integrated Process Team", 1999, *Department of Defense-United States of America*, retrieved from www.dtic.mil/cgi-bin/GetTRDoc?AD=ADA391380 □

2.5. CONCLUSION

This chapter has addressed the misuses of new communication technologies by first focusing on the types, then on the players involved in misuse. It has started the discussion by highlighting how social media are capable of making the misuses of media easier, faster and accessible to a wider range of individual and organizational actors. Then, the chapter discussed how new communication technologies can be used, intentionally and unintentionally, to misrepresent information in the context of political and man-made crises, and are also an effective tool to spread propaganda, and offering a tool to gather like-minded members of the public not only into physical squares but also virtual spaces.

The chapter also discussed how spread of rumours has been made faster and has the potential to reach out instantly to key publics with the use of social media, becoming itself a source of crisis as in the example of the rumour spread following the hacking Associated Press' Twitter account. The misuse of surveillance technologies, especially in the light of the landmark NSA/Snowden case, has revealed the reach and depth of such operations, justified on national security grounds.

Then, the role of the different players involved in the misuses of new media in the context of crises has been outlined, by looking into the use of hacking for malicious intents, as well as a form of activism. The role of scammers, in the phases preceding, coinciding and following natural disasters, and their actions aimed to divert donated funds from genuine charities have shown how new media can be misused to get money into the pockets of online criminals.

The use of digital technologies has been appropriated by governmental authorities that have been trying to prevent the use of new media as a mobiliser for protests during political crises, and to enact massive surveillance by forcing access into everyday online interactions of the users of the most popular US-based social networks.

The attention of the last section of the chapter has been pointed into the management and mismanagement of new media's misuse in the context of crises to show how various authorities have reacted to what they considered to be external threats as opposition movements, and foreign technology companies that have facilitated the networking and organization of those movements.

Also in this final section of the chapter, the concepts of sousveillance and countersurveillance have been discussed with respect to: 1) the use of new media for purposes of controlling the behaviour of local communities in situations of crisis caused by terroristic attacks; 2) the use of information technologies to make publics aware of the eventual excessive use of force by law enforcement agencies during crises; and, 3) the applications that, in the context of political crises, allow activists and reporters to avoid surveillance when it poses a danger to their lives or their personal freedom. The last section concluded with a discussion of management of internal threats, including misuse of communication and information technologies by insiders in an organization during, or to cause a, crisis; and technologies that aim to detect such behaviours in order to avoid or limit the consequences of a crisis.

3. INFORMATION RELIABILITY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

The focus of this chapter will be on the second main purpose of this report, which is to discuss the reliability of information disseminated via new communication technologies in the context of crises.

It will start by briefly exploring the concepts of information reliability and credibility before moving into the presentation explicative case studies in both traditional mass media and social media, in the latter case with an extended discussing of the use of social media use during the Gezi Park protests in Turkey in May/June 2013.

The final part will be then dedicated to the discussion of techniques and technologies for the verification of information, including the concept and practice of crowdsourcing and the review of a selection of new media applications that have been used in the context of crises as the Arab Spring, the Haiti Earthquake and Hurricane Sandy among others.

3.2. RELIABILITY AND CREDIBILITY

The concept of media credibility, their quality of being believable or worthy of trust, and media reliability, to be relied upon because of the accuracy and honesty in their production processes have been considered important aspects by the public in choosing their news sources among traditional broadcasting and print media. This aspect has acquired an even higher importance in the context of new communication and information technologies due to the exponential multiplication of what the internet users might consider as sources of information, including individual social media network accounts of trusted colleagues or friends.

In their review of media credibility theories, Nah and Chung have pointed out how media research has focused on the role of source credibility and trustworthiness, and to the increasing role of individual specialist blogs and issue-oriented websites in the new media context, gaining trust at the expense of traditional media.¹¹²

As the debate on media credibility and reliability “has received new-found popularity with the emergence of online news sources and the general migration of traditional media sources online” and is seen as “critical today as news readers are increasingly able to select from abundant sources”¹¹³, this aspect is important to be discussed in relation to potential misuses of communication technologies and conventional media in the context of crises

3.2.1. Mass Media

The issue of reliability and credibility of mass media organisations was examined in depth by the partners in COSMIC in the context of the 2010 Haiti Earthquake.¹¹⁴ The report underlined

¹¹² Seungahn, Nah and Chung, S. Deborah “When Citizens meet both professional and citizen journalists: Social trust, media credibility, and perceived journalistic roles among online community news readers”, *Journalism*, Vol.13, Issue 6, January 2012, pp.714-730.

¹¹³ Ibid., p.718

¹¹⁴ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., 2013, p.59-60

the threat to reliability of information posed by the increasing pressure on mainstream outlets to verify information at a much higher speed than in the past, due to the competition of social media in breaking the news

with social media breaking news within minutes of events occurring, the ability of mainstream media to ascertain the validity of content arriving from social media is small (while their own reporters will not be able to always be on-the-spot when, where and as major events occur). Thus, they are under pressure to use social media as sources, as fast as possible, while at the same time being aware that verifying the incoming information is difficult. There is a real risk of mainstream media erring on the side of speed rather than correctness and accuracy.¹¹⁵

For example, in the case of 2013 Boston Bombings such pressure were arguably the cause of CNN’s John King mistake in reporting that the police had identified and arrested a “dark-skinned male”, only to admit shortly later that “we don't know what's right or not right at this point.” (Figure 3)¹¹⁶

Figure 3: CNN Breaking News regarding the arrest of a “dark skinned male” was later retracted because it was false

Likewise, in the aftermath of the Mumbai attacks in 2008, credibility of coverage by BBC was questioned by critics who noted that it relied too heavily on citizen journalists (including microblogs) for updates. While BBC editor Steve Herman argued that such coverage provided ““a strong sense of what people connected in some way with the story were thinking and seeing”,¹¹⁷ such criticism has pushed news institutions like BBC to develop new approaches for news gathering in social media and new methods for verifying information.¹¹⁸

In Turkey, the Summer 2013 Gezi Park protests were also a “turning point for the credibility of Turkish media”¹¹⁹ by showing what has become the mock of the protesters and media analysts: the fact the CNN Turk, the local CNN outlet, was showing a documentary on

¹¹⁵ Ibid., pp.59-60

¹¹⁶ Coscarelli, John and Sara Frank, “Watch CNN Gradually Walk Back Its Reporting on the Nonexistent Boston Bombing Arrest”, *The New York Magazine*, retrieved from: <http://nymag.com/daily/intelligencer/2013/04/video-cnn-screws-up-boston-bomb-suspect-arrest.html>

¹¹⁷ Hermann, Steve, “Mumbai, Twitter and Live Updates”, *BBC*, 4 December 2008. http://www.bbc.co.uk/blogs/theeditors/2008/12/theres_been_discussion_see_eg.html

¹¹⁸ Watson, Hayley and Kush Wadhwa “The evolution of citizen journalism in crises: From crisis reporting to crisis management”, in Stuart Allan and Einar Thorsen (eds.), *Citizen Journalism: Global Perspectives, Volume Two*. Peter Lang. (Forthcoming)

¹¹⁹ Cesario, Marco, “Gezi-Park”: the media has lost all its credibility”, 11 June 2013, retrieved from <http://www.linkiesta.it/esra-arsan-media>

penguins while the main international channel, CNN International was reporting with a journalist directly from the scene of the protests in Istanbul’s Taksim Square (Figure 4).

Figure 4: CNN Turk and other mainstream news channels were heavily criticized for failing to report on the protests in their earlier phases. (Left: CNN Turk showing a documentary about penguins during the protest, Right: CNN Live coverage from protests)

As Turkish academic Esra Arsan remarked, “the major national media have completely overshadowed the police’s repression and deliberately ignored what was happening in the streets. They did not cover the news, they did not broadcast images or videos”¹²⁰

3.2.2. Social Media

The easy and unfiltered access to the publication of information on social media has been a cause of concern when examining the dynamics of communication of information during crises. On the one hand, as discussed earlier in this report, social media can be useful to crowdsource information from users located in the areas hit by a crisis, and relay it to public authorities.

However, this can also be a problem when the circulated information is not verified and checked before publication, a matter that has been pointed out by the partners in COSMIC when discussing the cases of Hurricane Sandy¹²¹ or the Haiti Earthquake.¹²²

It is within this context that the report by COSMIC underlined that “social media are not, currently, mission-critical grade telecommunications systems, but they are often relied upon heavily and they are often extremely useful, therefore researchers and governments should work towards graduating social media to the highest reliability and criticality levels of service.”¹²³

¹²⁰ Ibid.

¹²¹ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., 2013, p.48

¹²² Ibid., p.59

¹²³ Ibid., p.48

In Deliverable 2.2, the partners have summarized findings from a survey regarding how social media was utilized during the Gezi Park Protests in Turkey in 2013.¹²⁴ The survey also contained an open-ended question asking the respondents to report the types of “precautions” they had taken to verify the reliability of information they had seen on different social media sources.

As with open-ended questions summarized in the Chapter on Gezi Park Protests in Deliverable 2.2, grounded theory approach was utilized to code the answers that the users provided regarding how they verified information.¹²⁵ This involved a reiterative process of assigning answers to preliminary categories and then consolidating similar categories to identifying commonly appearing approaches.

Based on this analysis, it can be argued that there were two main types of approaches to ensure that the information that one received from social media was reliable. First, as summarized in Figure 5, one general approach to verifying the reliability of information can be characterized as “investigative” information verification methods. This approach involves checking the information received by doing additional search to gather new information that can help corroborate the information.

Most frequently (27%) respondents indicated that they directly contacted, via e-mail, Facebook, and often, via mobile phones, to verify the information they received from social media. Similarly, although not indicating which sources they would check, 26% of the respondents indicated that they would crosscheck the information with other sources.

Also, mass media were often reported to be utilized (22%) as sources for information verification. It should be noted that this finding regarding the use of mass media as a source of information verification, could be indicative of additional potential problems that can arise with respect to diffusion of false information.

As reported in case studies regarding Boston Bombings and Haiti Earthquake in Deliverable 2.2, often mass media outlets, in an effort to remain competitive by sharing up to date information, may sometimes fail to do sufficient fact-checking. For example, in the case of Boston Bombings, false information from the social media platform Reddit, filtered into the mass media when the *New York Post* printed the photos of two men as the culprits of the attacks.¹²⁶

Combined with the findings from this survey, the example from Boston Bombings, suggest that extensive reliance on mass media for verification of information may run the risk of amplifying existing false information by creating a feedback loop between social media dissemination and mass media coverage. Likewise, in the case of Gezi Protests, checking the level of diffusion of information as heuristic that indicates information reliability, which was used by 4% of the respondents, can also potentially lead to such amplification of false information.

Another important point to note about the use of “investigative verification of information” was the relatively less frequent use of technical/technological means of information

¹²⁴ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., pp.69-78

¹²⁵ Corbin, Juliet, and Anselm Strauss, *Basics of Qualitative Research: Grounded Theory Procedures and Techniques, ... Theory Procedures and Techniques*, Sage Publications, London, 1990.

¹²⁶ Papadimitriou, Alex et al., 2013, pp.14-25

verification. Most frequently, 9% of the respondents indicated that they used search engines to search for background information that can verify the information. Even less frequently, the respondents reported using metadata (e.g., time and location stamps) to infer about the reliability of information they received (3%) and used image authentication methods to verify the visuals (3%). For the latter category, Google Images and TinEye.com stood out as resources utilized for reverse image search and image authenticity verification.

It should also be noted that a relatively smaller percentage of participants indicated that rather than seeking more information to verify the existing information, they would focus their “investigative” capacities on finding out whether the source of the information can be trusted. For example, 9% of the respondents reported that once they receive a piece of questionable information they would do an online background check on the source of the information, which involves looking at the credibility of the information that the source had shared in the past. Likewise, 7% of the respondents indicated that the first thing they would do would be to search for the original source of the information.

Finally, although with small frequency, some respondents reported that their chosen method of information verification was to go “to the field” themselves to confirm the information on location (5%).

Figure 6 underlines a second general approach to addressing issues regarding reliability of information received from social media sources. This general approach, which can be named as “Convenience Verification”, comprises more passive methods that do not involve additional seeking of information.

The most common response within this category was that the “best” way to ensure the reliability of information was to only rely on sources that one already knows will not provide false information (11%). Respondents also indicated that simply waiting for information to disseminate and false information be filtered out by others would help them eliminate false information (5%).

Also, as shown in Figure 6, some (6%) of the respondents indicated that they would rely on information only with supporting visuals. This second method may often end-up misleading the users who do not engage in additional search to verify the authenticity of an image. This is because starting with the first day of the protests a number of widely circulated images turned out to be either taken out of context or from events unrelated to the Gezi Protests that were taking place in Turkey.

A case in point is the image shown on Figure 7. The image was alleged to be a proof of how a TOMA (translated as Intervention Vehicle for Social Events) ran over and injured a protestor. The vivid imagery combined with the infrequency with which users relied on reverse image search to verify the image caused its wide dissemination. In reality, however, this image was an image from a website that shows injuries from ParaMotor accidents.¹²⁷

¹²⁷ The survey was fielded online by COSMIC partner Koç University between June 10th and June 29th. Respondents were recruited via invitations, sent via e-mail, blogs, Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn. Individuals younger than 18 were not allowed to participate in the survey, which was completed by 329 respondents. The respondents were predominantly female (64%). The reported mean age of the respondents was 28 and the majority of them (54%) indicated that they were still students at a higher education institution (undergraduate or graduate). The partners believe that although the survey is not representative of the population or the protestors, the findings from the survey is more likely to be indicative of the social media usage patterns of Gezi Parkı protestors than the rest of the population.

Figure 7: This image is from a website that shows Paramotor injuries.¹²⁸ It was shared widely as a visual proof of how Police Vehicles ran over a protestor (The image was blurred for this report)

3.3. TECHNIQUES AND TECHNOLOGIES FOR VERIFICATION

The development of online sources that can rely on the expertise of crowds, rather than individual (or a group of) journalists and citizen reporters, as well as the potential offered by the availability of data in digital format has led to an increasing number of solutions that can be used for the verification of information.

In this section, we will proceed to outline and discuss the more general concept of crowdsourcing before moving into the illustration of a selection of available techniques and technologies for verification that include applications as Ushahidi, Ubalert, Checkdesk, Storyful, and Hoodcast, as well as infrastructural technologies as FOAF and SIOC.

3.3.1. Crowdsourcing

The development of new media technologies and social media networks has helped the establishment and development of crowdsourcing systems that help to resolve tasks in a collective manner, developing knowledge bases, and build maps.¹²⁹

Among other initiatives, the British daily newspaper *The Guardian*, made use of a large numbers of contributors to evaluate a large set of documents in a short window of time. In fact, on 18 June 2009 the House of Commons released 5,500 PDF files covering all the members of parliament and the newspaper wanted to “open up this data to as many people as

¹²⁸ Chiangmai ParaMotor, retrieved from <http://www.chiangmaiparamotor.com/forum/index.php?topic=3156.0>

¹²⁹ For a detailed discussion of the concept of Volunteered Geographic Information (VGI) see Goodchild, Michael F. and J. Alan Glennon, “Crowdsourcing geographic information for disaster response: a research frontier”, *International Journal of Digital Earth*, Vol.3, Issue 3, September 2010, pp.231-241.

possible” in order to help them to “analyse it and find the great stories buried within the photocopied handwritten receipts”¹³⁰ Given that mass of data, and the impossibility to analyze them in relatively short time with its own professional resources, it asked its like-minded readers to collaborate in a crowdsourcing exercise that had also the aim to make the English lawmakers more accountable and produce news content for the newspaper itself.

Elsewhere in COSMIC, crowdsourcing has been discussed in more detail by listing applications that are being used in the context of crisis management, describing it as referring “to those individuals, often volunteers, who choose to use their skills and knowledge to perform certain tasks that contribute to the response efforts in a crisis”¹³¹.

In the context of the Haiti Earthquake, for example, a platform as Ushahidi, emerged as an useful tool for “the sharing of information, request and [to] provide assistance and organise response efforts by mapping relevant information in real-time”¹³². Ushahidi a free and open source platform, includes technologies as Crowdmapper that help to built in short time tools to map crisis information by crowdsourcing it¹³³.

The Haiti Earthquake is examined more in detail in COSMIC in D 2.2 when case on the use of new media in crisis situations are discussed. And here is pointed how the use of social media and crowdsourcing combines provided “a huge flow of unorganised, unverified information,”¹³⁴ but also how, to a certain extent, crowdsourcing helped to vet the information (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Screenshot of Ushahidi after the Haiti Earthquake¹³⁵

¹³⁰ Rogers, Simon “How to crowdsource MPs expenses”, *The Guardian*, 18 June 2009, retrieved from <http://www.guardian.co.uk/news/datablog/2009/jun/18/mps-expenses-houseofcommons>

¹³¹ Watson, Hayley; Finn, Rachel; Wadhwa, Kush; Yannopoulos, Angelos, “Deliverable 2.1: Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications”, *COSMIC* 2013, pp.47-52

¹³² Watson, Hayley et al., 2013, pp.51-52

¹³³ “Welcome”, *Crowdmap*, 2013, <https://crowdmap.com/>

¹³⁴ Yannopoulos, Angelos, ‘Deliverable 2.2: Haiti Earthquake, January 2010

¹³⁵ Keegan, Victor, “Meet the Wikipedia of the Mapping World”, *The Guardian*, 4 February 2010, retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/technology/2010/feb/04/mapping-open-source-victor-keegan>

Indeed, for the purposes of this report, the review will be limited to their use for the verification of information. In this context, the use of crowdsourcing methods and volunteer contributions from interested users and the general public does pose some challenges with regards to the reliability of information and the possible infiltration of malicious users. Crowdsourcing management tools can help in this task, as Doan et al. suggest in their review

Manual techniques include monitoring the system by the owners, distributing the monitoring workload among a set of trusted users, and enlisting ordinary users (such as flagging bad contributions on message boards) (...) we can deter malicious users with threats of “punishment.” A common punishment is banning. A newer, more controversial form of punishment is “public shaming,” where a user U judged malicious is publicly branded as a malicious or “crazy” user for the rest of the community.¹³⁶

Indeed, the concepts of quality, accuracy and reliability are central issues in the overall discussion of crowdsourcing methods, whether it applies to news provided by citizen journalists, witnesses or to information added to maps and other geospatial tools.

Quoting the questions raised by Goodchild and Glennon when discussing maps, emergencies and Volunteered Geographical Information (VGI), “If the providers of VGI are not experts, and if they operate under no institutional or legal frameworks, then how can one expect the results of VGI creation and publication to be accurate?”¹³⁷ This, they argue, reflects “the deep association society makes between qualifications, institutions, and trust.”¹³⁸ They also underline the importance of a clear “hierarchy of volunteers who employ well-defined criteria that are appropriate to crowdsourcing”¹³⁹ as in the case of Wikipedia.¹⁴⁰

Like-minded people, a well designed platform, and the possibility to validate the reliability of information constitute an important part of the crisis management process where the information is verified and then is used to help agencies and responders organize their work more efficiently. Such mechanisms help to avoid also the so-called “cry wolf” effect, a non-compliant warning behavior that might be expected from individuals who have responded to too many “false alarm” warning messages,¹⁴¹ and be particularly useful in crises that originate from natural disasters.

3.3.2. FOAF and SIOC

The Friend of a Friend (FOAF) project aims to create a website with “machine-readable pages describing people, the links between them and the things they create and do (...) an open, decentralized technology for connecting social Web sites.”¹⁴² It is considered to be the first Social Semantic Web application and aims to facilitate users to share knowledge. Importantly,

¹³⁶ Doan, Anhai; Raghu Ramakrishnan and Alon Y. Halevy, “Crowdsourcing Systems on the Web”, *Communications of the ACM*, Vol. 54, Issue 4, April 2011, pp.86-96 [p.95].

¹³⁷ Goodchild, Michael F. and J. Alan Glennon, “Crowdsourcing geographic information for disaster response: a research frontier”, *International Journal of Digital Earth*, Vol.3, Issue 3, September 2010, pp.231-241 [p.235].

¹³⁸ *Ibid.*, p.235

¹³⁹ *Ibid.*, p.236.

¹⁴⁰ This is contrasted with the case of Wikimapia, where ‘The complexity of the project and the obscurity of many features made it difficult for crowdsourcing mechanisms to work to correct errors (...)As the volume of errors increases and crowdsourcing mechanisms fail to assure quality, the reputation of the site begins to deteriorate. Eventually the motivation to maintain the site is impacted and the site fails’ (*Ibid.*)

¹⁴¹ Sorensen. John, and Vogt, Barbara, *Interactive Emergency Evacuation Guidebook*, 2006

¹⁴² Home Page, *The Friend of a Friend Project*, 2013, retrieved from <http://www.foaf-project.org/>

for the purposes of this report, it is a technique that could help in the verification of information in newsgathering processes.

Linked to the FOAF, the SIOC (Semantically-Interlinked Online Communities) project aims to enable the integration of online community information, in order to interconnect blogs, forums and mailing lists to each other, and in an open-standard machine-readable format. SIOC, by “becoming a standard way for expressing user-generated content from such sites, SIOC enables new kinds of usage scenarios for online community site data, and allows innovative semantic applications to be built on top of the existing Social Web.”¹⁴³

Both FOAF and SIOC contribute to what has been named as Social Semantic Journalism and “has the potential to create a network of interlinked and semantically enriched user-generated knowledge-base, bringing together applications and social features of the Social Web with knowledge representation languages and formats from the Semantic Web.”¹⁴⁴

Heravi et al. have underlined the importance of exploring ways SIOC and FOAF “could assist in the process of interlinking online user communities and the user-generated content for news gathering and verification” and extend it to the news industry, so that “Semantic and Social Web in conjunction with journalism, news and the media industry for achieving a more coherent way for newsgathering and verification.”¹⁴⁵

In the context of crisis management, SIOC and FOAF can then support the development technologies that can facilitate the processes of verification of information, one of most important issues in the social newsgathering process that media outlets use when reporting crises. However, a limit of this solution is, at this time, the implementation of such standards into the websites that are the sources of the social newsgathering process. Only after the adoption by a large number of players the eventual benefits could be analysed more comprehensively and show the possible implications for crisis management.

3.3.3. Ubalert

A tool that helps to verify the reliability of information, outlined in the discussion of crowdsourcing in COSMIC’s D2.1 is Ubalert, “a social network of individuals, working together via crowdsourcing activities to share knowledge of the world’s crises that could affect the security of citizens.”¹⁴⁶ Apart from its web presence, Ubalert includes a global emergency platform (mobile app) that “validates the reliability of the reported content and then immediately alerts those who may be impacted, depending on the severity and location.”¹⁴⁷

¹⁴³ Home Page, *SIOC Project-Semantically Interlinked Online Communities*, 2013, retrieved from <http://sioc-project.org/>

¹⁴⁴ Rahmanzadeh Heravi, Bahareh; Boran, Marie; Breslin, John G., “Towards Social Semantic Journalism”, *AAAI Technical Report WS-12-01 - The Potential of Social Media Tools and Data for Journalists in the News Media Industry*, 2012, pp.14.17 [p.16]

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid.*, p.17.

¹⁴⁶ Watson, Hayley; Finn, Rachel; Wadhwa, Kush; Yannopoulos, Angelos, ‘Deliverable 2.1: Baseline analysis of communication technologies and their applications, 2013, [p.52]

¹⁴⁷ “About us”, *Ubalert*, 2013. http://www.ubalert.com/about_us

Figure 9: Screenshot from Ubalert

3.3.4 Checkdesk

A technology developed by Meedan, a “non-profit social technology company” based in San Francisco¹⁴⁸, Checkdesk is a platform that was developed to help newsrooms across the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region to “to work with citizen journalists to validate, translate, and contextualize social media content”¹⁴⁹.

During the course of the Arab Spring, professional journalists were (and still are in other political crises) flooded by user generated content allegedly originating from area hit by crises and were confronted with the issue of verification of content being posted on Youtube or other video sharing platforms.

This technology attempts to “facilitate collaborative verification” by building a community of volunteer (citizen) reporters capable “of jointly providing lots of pieces of small information”, so that “the journalist can better sort the accurate and important content from the dangerous, misleading or doctored content”¹⁵⁰.

3.3.5 Storyful

Storyful originates from a team of technology experts and journalists spread between the USA, Europe and Asia, including veteran journalists from mainstream media, as well as younger professionals, who are specialized in social newsgathering and have put together a tool that helps to separate the social media noise from reliable information.¹⁵¹

The group describes its Dashboard product as a tool that “allows media organisations to discover, validate and deliver actionable news content from the real-time web” and claims that its “contacts database compiles on-the-ground sources so you can immediately call on the person closest to the story”¹⁵². This tool has gathered mainstream media attentions as it is

¹⁴⁸ “About”, Meedan, 2013. <http://meedan.org/about/>

¹⁴⁹ Ibid.

¹⁵⁰ “Checkdesk: A new approach to fact-checking citizen media of the Arab Spring”, Meedan, 2013. <http://meedan.org/2012/03/verification-citizen-journalism-middle-east-uprisings/>

¹⁵¹ “Our Products”, Storyful, 2013, <http://storyful.com/our-products/>

¹⁵² Ibid.

being used by, among others, organizations as Reuters, New York Times, ABC, BBC and France24, and has been used in crises as the Syria War and Hurricane Sandy¹⁵³.

3.3.6 Hoodcast

A mobile application that has made the credibility of the information it makes its users publish and share is Hoodcast. Developed in Istanbul, Turkey, the application claims that “Each cast is created by a real user, in real time with proof and accurate location.”¹⁵⁴ This “network of news,” states that it gives users “the opportunity to access the news [called Casts] from the first source. (...) Every cast must have at least a photo and information regarding the news. Casts are processed by the system based on their location and then evaluated according to the reader trend.”

The relevance of such an application for crisis management resides in the possibility to make available a set of metadata from which news outlets and Internet users could verify the reliability of information with regards to, at least the time and location of each cast or picture, a matter that is the focus also of other applications like the one described next.

3.4. CONCLUSION

This chapter, exploring the concept of reliability in new media, and its connected concept of credibility has started by stating how reliability has become an even more important concept in the context of new media. At this time, the actors that have access to social media and communication tools that can reach instantly from local to global audiences have also changed the communicative dynamics during periods of crisis.

It has been discussed how mass media, in the heat of the increasing competition of online news media outlets in the delivery of breaking news have had spectacular failings in giving space to speculations, rather than verified facts (the Boston bombings suspect hunting), as well losing credibility when ignoring large demonstrations as during the Gezi Park protests in Turkey in the summer of 2013. A research carried out as part of Deliverable 2.2 in COSMIC was then briefly discussed, including the outcome of a research by one of the partners (KU) on the use of tools for the verification of information in social media during the Gezi Park protests, was also summarized.

Finally, the last section of the chapter reviewed the technologies and techniques available for information verification by first illustrating the concept of crowdsourcing. Then, a number of applications that have been successfully used in the context of crises to help the verification of the information provided by local users was discussed, highlighting the practical implications of their use in terms of both informing the public as well as the work of first responders to the disaster/crisis stricken area.

4. CONCLUSION

The way media can be relied upon for information production, access, and sharing have changed profoundly with the advent of new communication and information technologies. The outreach and relative ease of access to global platforms and social networks of

¹⁵³ “Superstorm Sandy: Verifying the videos and images with Storyful”, *YouTube*, 2012,

<http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NDc4-W8qMC8#t=39>

¹⁵⁴ “About”, *Hoodcast*, 2013 <http://hoodcast.com/stream/about>

communication offer new opportunities for emergency response. Yet, particularly in the context of crises and emergencies, such technologies can often be used adversely in ways that intentionally or unintentionally impede emergency response and harm communities and individuals.

This report provided an overview of adverse use of communication and information technologies and issues related to reliability of information disseminated through new media (and particularly social media). This findings from this report regarding the adverse use of and reliability of information in new media, along with guideline principles are summarized below.

- All the players involved in the adverse use of media hackers, scammers, government authorities and private corporations, have at their disposal much more powerful tools than anytime in the past. These tools can be utilized for various insidious purposes as well as to respond to and manage misuse of media.

Types of Misuse of Information and Communication Technologies

- **Misrepresentation:** Social media use can facilitate the spread of misleading information and misrepresent the individuals or groups. In case of man-made crises such as terrorist attacks, this can quickly evolve into a “witch-hunt” which, if uncontrolled, can lead to unsubstantiated allegations that can harm innocent individuals, their families and community groups.

- **Rumours:** New communication technologies can be particularly effective in spreading rumours faster, enlarging their outreach to a global audience and, most importantly, making this possible for a much larger pool of users, potentially everybody with a social media network account. The spread of rumours of a non-existing crisis, through the hack of a newswire agency, caused a crisis itself and resulted in real financial losses.

Guideline Principle

Actors involved in emergency response and crisis communications need to actively monitor the social media to identify and correct misinformation that are related to their functions and pre-empt fraudulent activities that may be linked to their organization without their knowledge.

Currently, many corporations actively use social media monitoring services to gauge public opinion about themselves on social media. Such media monitoring services utilize techniques like natural language processing to identify opportunities and threats for the organizations. Similar techniques may be helpful for key stakeholders to identify false information involving their organizations.

- **Scammers** are increasingly using new media tools to attract unaware users that end up transferring funds that helps to finance their online criminal activities rather than relief efforts during natural crises. Private corporations have also used new media in the context of political and natural crises to pursue what have been judges as highly unethical techniques of marketing and public relations to raise their sales or brand popularity.
- **Propaganda:** During crises, various players, like authoritarian regimes, criminal and terrorist groups can use the Internet and social networks to rapidly disseminate

propaganda. In situations of crisis, national governments have been observed to use such platforms to fortify their position on a particular matter, which can include the feeding of nationalistic feelings.

- Surveillance and censorship:** As new media use relies heavily on telecommunication infrastructures, often controlled or heavily influenced by government authorities policies and actions, there is a cause of concern when such powers are used to limit the freedom or the communicative actions of users, especially in times of political crises. The revelations made by the Snowden leaks regarding NSA surveillance programs, still unfolding at the time of writing, has brought to the light the extent and depth of surveillance on ordinary citizens. In a crisis context, the fact that national agencies, and private companies working on their behalf, can have access to enormous sets of data that record detailed information of users' activities without their knowledge and consent may have important consequences for democratic rights such as freedom of association and freedom of speech. Related to surveillance, the use of censorship for bloggers and activists that use new media tools has been widely used, especially in countries with high levels of authoritarianism.

Guideline Principle

The ease with which information about individuals flows across national borders make it increasingly difficult for individuals to protect their privacy. As the NSA leaks suggest, in many cases corporations may become an unwitting participant in the state surveillance of communication. This may particularly be the case during political crises when states are driven by the motivation to silent dissent.

As such, involvement of supranational organizations in protecting communicational privacy of individuals may be needed to shield individuals, and private corporations, from misuse by national governments.

- Relatedly, in responding to other man-made crises, such as in the aftermath of terrorist attacks, **lateral surveillance** may also create unintended consequences. This was the case in the wake of the Boston Bombings when social media users, in trying to identify the perpetrators, misidentified an individual as being the culprit. Such incidents run the risk of leading to “witch-hunting” and a more general climate of suspicion.
- Hacking** has been used to steal sets of sensible information that can potentially hand in malicious hands, and for purposes of cyberwarfare in the context of political crises, but has also a more positive function since it can be used to those who make and adverse use of new media more accountable.

Management of misuse of information and communication technologies

- The management and mismanagement of the adverse use of media includes the management of both external and internal threats. The report conceptualized external threats as those that come from the outside a given system or organization. The report also indicated that particularly at times of crises, organizations might, themselves, be victims of misuse from individuals within that organization.
- With respect to management of external threats, the section on management of misuse of ICTs has shown that there is a thin line between responding to potential misuse of ICTs

and engaging in activities that may themselves impede on crisis communications. In this respect We have outlined how government agencies may respond to what they consider as adverse utilization of ICTs by pushing for a complete shutdown of all telecommunications infrastructures that make the use of new media tools impossible, or very difficult. This is particularly the case for political crises when authoritarian regimes attempted to silence dissent and isolate oppositional movements.

- At the same time, increasing utilization of social media and mobile technologies for sousveillance have made it possible for individuals to hold powerful institutions more accountable. Such an ability is of particular importance in limiting use of excessive force during political crises.
- Likewise, technologies that assist countersurveillance are also of critical importance in protecting individual liberties during crises by implementing solutions that make surveillance more difficult.
- In the case of management of internal threats, organizations are increasingly more at risk from the possible misbehaviour of insiders that can steal and share confidential information, leading to, or to the worsening of, a situation of crisis can be limited by technologies that can help to detect such behaviour at an early stage.

Guideline Principle

Increasing the accessibility of and publics' knowledge about sousveillance and countersurveillance tools is of critical importance in protecting freedom of speech and freedom of association.

Reliability of information new media

- Individuals' and organizations' increased access to online publication platforms along with the increasing use of social media as a source of information is changing the way Internet users learn about events and the unfolding of crisis. Partly as a result of the types of misuses described in the report (e.g., propaganda, rumour spreading) extended reliance on social media platforms increases the likelihood that unverified information can circulate widely before being confirmed or rejected by reliable sources.
- While, conventional mass media have the potential to alleviate the problem of misinformation by filtering false information, our analyses suggest that at times, as a result of having to compete with online information sources, mass media have rushed into the publication, and consequently contributed to the circulation of unverified, and often false, information.
- Additionally, in countries with higher level of authoritarianism, mass media have been the target of criticism for ignoring the unfolding of political crises in order to avoid the awareness on such events to a larger public. In the long run, what is at stake is the credibility of mass media as a fourth estate.

Guideline Principle

Standardization and widespread adoption of information verification tools for journalists is a prerequisite for maintaining the viability of mass media organizations as a reliable source of information. Otherwise, particularly at times of crises, mass media risk turning into another cog in a wheel of misinformation

- The findings of the research on social media use during the Gezi Park Protest in Turkey in June 2013, suggest that citizens are highly aware of the potential pitfalls of information they see on social media. They actively try to verify information using various methods. However, effectiveness of such methods are questionable. In many cases, they are based on heuristics that may end up leading to further dissemination of false information.

Guideline Principle

Citizens are already aware of the need to verify information but the techniques they use may not always be as effective as they hope.

Further research is required to determine, more systematically, the extent to which the techniques used by citizens and other stakeholders to verify information can effectively help increase information reliability. Such research can help develop better tools that can be used by citizens and other stakeholders to verify information.

- The findings of the research on social media use during the Gezi Park Protest in Turkey in June 2013, suggest that extensive reliance on mass media for verification of information may run the risk of amplifying existing false information by creating a feedback loop between social media dissemination and mass media coverage.

- New media have also brought new and potentially more effective sources for the verification of information based on crowdsourcing efforts, which can process effectively large quantities of data in digital format. This has meant that, in situations of crises, such tools can be used to support improved disaster relief efforts by directing help where is needed most, but also to distinguish noise from true information in the process of social media newsgathering by triangulating data about an event during an unfolding crisis.

Guideline Principle

Examples suggest that crowdsourcing applications have already proven beneficial in the context of crises prompted by natural or political events. However, their full utilization will depend on whether they can reach a critical mass of users (both sources and readers). Interoperability of such crowdsourcing applications may be a key to achieving this goal.

ACRONYMS**F**

FOAF Friend Of A Friend

I

ICT Information and Communication Technology

IT Information Technology

L

LOF Local Outlier Factor

N

NBC National Broadcasting Company

S

SIOC Semantically Interlinked Online Communities

V

VGI Volunteered Geographic Information